
ASSESSMENT OF WORK VALUES ON RESTAURANT EMPLOYEES IN OLONGAPO CITY

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to assess the factors of work values on Restaurant Employees in Olongapo City. Researchers used the Purposive Sampling Method with a quantitative study design. Data is collected using survey questionnaires made up of a checklist and a 4-point Likert Scale to collect information from Full-time Regular Restaurant Employees in Olongapo City. The sample population of this research is composed of 240 Employees aged 18 to 65 working in Cafes and casual and fast-food restaurants. The examination of the results of the demographic profile reveals that most of the respondents are aged 23-27 Years Old (37.1%), Female (55.4%), attained College Level (38.8%), Rank and File Job Title (75.8%), and have P8,001-P11,999 (60.8%) Monthly Income. The findings show that the respondents had high work values in hedonism, security, self-transcendence, openness to change, and self-enhancement. Upon examination of significant differences in factors of work values when grouped according to profile, the test shows significant differences in terms of gender (conservation and security), educational attainment (self-enhancement), job title (self-enhancement and openness to change), and monthly income (self-enhancement). Researchers conclude that employees in Olongapo City possess High Work Values. Self-enhancement is the most significant factor that drives employees toward achieving professional achievement, competence, and success. The results of this study serve as the foundation for developing a work values-formation program. This study can also assist the Local Government Unit and the Human Resource Management of the business in developing employees' professional achievement and wellbeing.

Keywords: factors of work values, professional achievement, competence, success, and employee wellbeing.

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INTRODUCTION

Work values are a fundamental component of a person's professional identity and significantly impact the dynamics of the workplace, business culture, and overall performance. Work Values are a belief and a sense of optimism that an individual has as a principle that directs and encourages him to do a job (Yulistiani et al., 2020). Understanding, preserving, and incorporating these values can result in a workforce that is more engaged, content, and productive as well as a business that is more in line with its goals and mission. Personal values and motivation are intimately connected, which helps to explain behavior (Cieciuch, 2017). Therefore, when making judgments, selecting actions, and defending their behavior, employees are willing to rely on their values (Arieli & Tenne-Gazit, 2017).

Individual values impact employees' workplace behavior (Gonzalez-Rodriguez et al., 2014). Furthermore, when a person's work aligns with his or her beliefs, they can work toward having more autonomy there. It has been shown that personal values form in a person's formative years and then remain largely steady over time (Vecchione et al., 2015, 2016; Cieciuch et al., 2016).

According to Purc and Laguna (2019), the first ten fundamental values can be divided into the following two bipolar dimensions: openness to change (self-direction and stimulation) versus conservation (tradition, conformity, and security) and self-transcendence (universalism and benevolence) versus self-enhancement (power and achievement); hedonistic values incorporate elements of both dimensions.

Sagiv and Schwartz (1995) suggested the following broad definitions to represent better an organizational context: Power (POW) is a value that entails valuing one's social standing, achieving a prominent or authoritative position, wanting to have more power over other members of the organization or enhance one's influence, and acquiring resources. Achievement (ACH) and development, as well as proving one's competence in light of cultural and contextual norms (e.g., ability, experience, ambition), are implied by upholding this ideal. Hedonism (HED) is a value that emphasizes finding fulfillment, enjoyment, and pleasure in one's work life, as well as making sure that one's work does not conflict with one's personal or recreational time. Stimulation (STI) refers to a value that highlights the value of challenge, novelty, curiosity, and exploration, all of which excite one's professional life and lead to discovering new and interesting sources. Self-direction (SDI) is a value that emphasizes the potential for people to be able to freely express themselves at work, think for themselves, act independently, use their creativity, and fully utilize and display their intelligence. Universalism (UNI) adherence to this principle establishes the significance of adopting an accommodating, perceptive, protective, and appreciating stance toward others (colleagues inside the company and, more broadly, individuals one encounters). Benevolence (BEN) in this value type shows how important it is to actively commit to promoting the wellbeing of everyone with whom one interacts during one's professional activities. This term shows one is sincere, honest, willing to assist, and accountable. Tradition (TRA) values strongly emphasize contextual

habits and conventions, adherence to thought patterns, and solidifying commitment to maintaining cultural tradition. Conformity (CON) is a virtue that entails following norms, expectations, and social pressure. It shows self-control and "loyalty" to elders' advice, but it also limits one's network of behaviors and/or shapes one's preferences, inclinations, urges, and desires. Moreover, Security (SEC) value means maintaining harmony, stability, order, and security in the workplace, interpersonal interactions, and professional activities.

Based on the study of Cena et al. (2021), Cervera (1988) stated that some of the values from Schwartz' Theory (1992) are similar to the Filipino Work Values Scale. First, there is the intellectual-achievement orientation, which is associated with the capacity for independent thought, the understanding of how and why things function, and the satisfaction that comes from a job well done; second, there is the interpersonal orientation, which is related to people and encompasses ideas such as "*amor proprio*," "*hiya*," "*utang na loob*," going between, using intermediaries, and the significance of loyalty, hospitality, emotional closeness, and respect for authority; third, there is the managerial orientation, which involves allocating human and material resources to accomplish the objectives of a work organization; fourth, there is the material orientation, which enables one to enjoy financial returns, prestige, and security. Fifth, occupational orientation is related to pursuing one's profession. Public service, skill, competency, altruism, and occupational autonomy are all included in this.

To begin with, the focal objective of this research study is to resolve the local literature gap about the work values study and contribute to forming a work values program in the community of Olongapo City among employees of dining restaurants. This research study enables the hospitality sector to clearly understand the factors of work values in an employee's professional achievement and wellbeing. In addition, this study aims to assist the Local Government Unit of Olongapo City in addressing work-related issues and concerns about employee's job security and safety. The results of this study contribute to the existing knowledge of our research gap.

Literature Review

When people support and put into practice their original ideas, they can reach goals associated with power and achievement values. By engaging in these activities, individuals can elevate their status inside the company and enhance their reputation among coworkers and superiors. Additionally, Taştan and Davoudi (2017) showed that both power and achievement values positively influenced organizational innovativeness among workers in managerial positions. According to Anjum et al. (2014), there is a significant positive link between self-improvement values and the most prevalent management style, a leadership style that emphasizes the use of authority, power, and control. Employees who adhere to these self-improvement principles are motivated by a desire for power and naturally look for leadership roles. This condition seems to align with the culture that permeates many restaurants, where both restaurant managers and

chefs/cooks might believe that employing this management style is the only way to accept responsibility and guarantee the performance of hospitality businesses.

Self-transcendent values prioritize the wellbeing of others and the environment. They demonstrate a person's fundamental need to build relationships with other individuals (Arieli & Tenne-Gazit, 2017). Values of self-transcendence impact conduct that is contrary to values of achievement, hedonism, and power.

According to Tamir et al. (2016), those prioritizing conservation are likelier to exhibit the Big Five personality qualities of agreeableness, conscientiousness, emotional stability, serenity, and reduced fear. In addition, previous research has also shown that jobs held by people with lower socioeconomic status tend to be more conservative, whereas those held by employees who advance to positions of greater responsibility are frequently permeated with values associated with openness to change (i.e., varied and exciting life, creativity, daring, independence, freedom, and choosing one's own goals). Previous studies have demonstrated that there is a connection between a higher level of responsibility at work and a greater willingness to change. This connection is notably linked to transformational leadership (Ariza-Montes et al., 2017). Indeed, scholars have argued that openness to change values is connected to innovation and creativity due to their motivating meanings (Arieli & Tenne-Gazit, 2017), and prior empirical research has supported these claims.

According to Nagda (2023), the pursuit of pleasure, or hedonism, can influence workplace culture in both positive and harmful ways. Suppose employees are permitted to engage in pleasure-seeking activities during work hours or as part of work-related events. In that case, it can enhance motivation and job satisfaction. They may only need a morale boost to feel more satisfied with their work. Coworker relationships may improve as a result. Team-building activities, corporate getaways, and team lunches are just a few of the events that can help enhance relationships between coworkers and boost productivity. Well, it might not always have been a strong force for good and occasionally might have also accompanied negative. Hedonistic pursuits can reduce overall productivity if they occupy too much time or distract the workers.

Employees' health and wellbeing may be among the most important elements for organizational success and performance (Bakker et al., 2019; Turban & Yan, 2016). Employees' well-being has been linked in numerous studies to a variety of positive individual and organizational outcomes, including better customer satisfaction, employee engagement, organizational citizenship behavior, and organizational performance and productivity (Hewett et al., 2018; Sharma et al., 2016; Tisu et al., 2020).

The confidence that one will be employed permanently is known as job security. It has to do with the employee's perception of losing their job or losing desirable workplace advantages like chances for job progression and promotion, favorable working conditions, possibilities for career training and development, and attractive pay. A person's commitment to an organization depends on their ability to keep their job, which impacts their dedication. Employees who feel safe in their jobs and the organization are more

committed to both. Employee connection to their jobs is called job security (Ogunbanjo, 2021).

According to Artz and Kaya (2014), job security, which may affect employee job satisfaction in an organization, is often calculated using the alleged likelihood of future job loss. They argue that job stability influences job satisfaction, not just a result of a person losing their job and finding another. This impact on employees' job happiness varies depending on the apparent job loss occurrence and openings in other firms.

Schwartz's Theory of Basic Values

Schwartz's Theory outlines ten core principles guiding human behavior: power, achievement, hedonism, stimulation, self-direction, universalism, benevolence, tradition, conformity, and security.

Research on Schwartz's Portrait Values Questionnaire in work contexts revealed significant differences in age, gender, and education levels. Young adults prioritize self-transcendence and conservation values over self-enhancement and hedonism. At the same time, men emphasize self-enhancement, and women focus on self-transcendence and security. Education impacts conservation and openness to change values, with less educated individuals valuing tradition more and those with higher education valuing openness to change. Notably, all participants equally value security and self-improvement in the workplace (Farnese, 2010).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researchers used a quantitative research design. Researchers aim to describe the factors of work values when grouped according to profile by assessing and interpreting the gathered numerical data from the sample through a questionnaire. According to Asio (2021), this research involves understanding specific characteristics of a phenomenon or sample of a population in terms of numerical representation. This type of research usually uses statistical tools/instruments, either descriptive and/or inferential, to deal with the data gathered from the samples involved in the study. Simply put, the researchers intend to quantify or explore a research issue and then use it to evaluate the outcomes of the data collected. This study assessed the work values of Casual, Cafe, and fast-food restaurant employees in Olongapo City.

Research Respondents

The study included 240 full-time regular employees aged 18 to 65 working in Olongapo City's casual, cafe, and fast-food restaurants. The profile of employees includes information on their age, gender, job title, degree of education, and monthly income. Additionally, part-time, contract, temporary, on-call, seasonal, intern, and volunteer workers in dining establishments were excluded from this research study. Researchers

used a Purposive Sampling Method. The most suitable moment to use purposeful sampling is when researchers wish to concentrate carefully on small samples. Perhaps researchers are researching a topic that contains uncommon instances and would like to access a specific subset of the population with certain characteristics. Finding the examples, people, or communities most suited to assist researchers in answering the research issue is the significant objective of purposive sampling (Nikolopoulou, 2022). In addition, the researchers computed the optimal sample size using G* Power, which was 240 samples, power = 0.80, and effect size = 0.25. The chance of effectively rejecting the null hypothesis is the definition of a statistical test's power (Cohen, 1988). The study's sample size impacts the sample values' dependability and, specifically, on how closely the sample values should resemble population values. It also establishes the significance criterion, typically $\alpha = 0.05$, and the magnitude of the effect. Furthermore, 0.80 is the commonly acknowledged minimum power level (Cohen, 1988). With an effect size of 0.25 and a significance level 0.05, 240 is the ideal sample size.

Research Instrument

The primary tool for data collection is a questionnaire. Researchers adopted a structured questionnaire based primarily on The Work Values Questionnaire (WVQ) (Consiglio et al., 2017), which was developed for a study that sought to capture the ten values conceptualized by the Theory of Basic Personal Values (Schwartz, 1992) and adapt them to a work-related setting.

The focal data collection technique used is a checklist questionnaire. The questionnaire is divided into two (2) parts: Part I collects data on the respondents' profiles, including (1.1) age, (1.2) gender, (1.3) educational attainment, (1.4) job title, and (1.5) monthly income. The factors of work values on employees described in Part II are (2.1) self-enhancement, (2.2) self-transcendence, (2.3) conservation, (2.4) openness to change, (2.5) hedonism, and (2.6) security.

The adopted work values questionnaire consists of 30 items and required scale responses ranging from 1-4, with (4) as the highest and (1) being the lowest. The instrument used a 4-point Likert Scale. 4 shows "Strongly Agree" with a descriptive interpretation of "With High Work Values"; 3 shows "Agree" and "With Moderate Work Values"; 2 is "Disagree" and "With Low Work Values"; and 1 "Strongly Disagree" and "With Lowest Work Values." The respondents provided copies of survey questionnaires to 240 full-time regular restaurant employees aged between 18 and 65 in casual, cafe, and fast-food restaurants. This structured questionnaire undergoes Two Factor Analysis. The first one yielded six value dimensions wherein Cronbach's alpha value suggests that they are internally consistent (alpha were all $>.70$) except for the one involving security. The second one, using the EQS software, Confirmatory Factor Analysis, was performed to test the factor structure that resulted from the exploratory factor analysis under more stringent assumptions (Ullman & Bentler, 2003). The theoretical framework comprises the six incidental elements from the investigational factor analysis. The proposed model's

goodness of fit indices produced an acceptable range. Avallone et al. (2010) states that the Work Values Questionnaire is a viable and reliable tool. The current findings supported the measure's internal consistency. The Work Values Questionnaire could be a helpful tool for investigating and comprehending the world of values in a particular setting, learning about a particular organizational or social reality, and learning about work-related ideals and desired future employment.

Data Analysis

The researchers used Excel 2019 and SPSS 26 for data entry to organize the information collected from the respondents—a non-parametric test for the non-normal distribution of groups in the statistical approach. For data analysis and interpretation presented in Chapter 3, the researchers employed frequency, percentage, mean, Shapiro-Wilk, Kruskal-Wallis, and Post Hoc tests. The researchers employed frequency and percentage to get data on respondents' age, gender, job title, level of education, and monthly income. In addition, the mean determined the descriptive interpretation of factors of work values and its indicators. The Shapiro-Wilk Test was used to test the normality of group distribution. The Kruskal-Wallis H Test ascertains whether there were statistically significant differences between two or more groups. Lastly, the Post Hoc Test presents the Kruskal-Wallis pairwise comparison between subgroups because of the significant results found in the test.

Ethical Consideration

The study required the participation of human respondents, specifically restaurant employees, and ethical issues to be addressed. Considering this article, the issue will be necessary to ensure the privacy and safety of respondents. The significant ethical issues considered in the research process include consent and confidentiality. The research consent of the selected respondents conveys all essential details of the study, including its aim and purpose. By explaining these details, the respondents understood the importance of their role in completing this research study. The respondents were advised that they could withdraw from the study even during the process. These respondents were not forced to participate in the research. The confidentiality of the respondents was ensured by not disclosing the names of personal information in the study. Only relevant details that help in answering the research questions were included.

This research complies with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173) to protect personal information. The researchers ensured voluntary participation by providing respondents with a consent letter that outlined the study's objectives, procedures, and risks. Explicit consent was obtained for data collection, storage, and processing, with measures in place to safeguard privacy and prevent unauthorized access. Data is securely stored and retained only as necessary for the study after it has been disposed of securely. Respondents were informed of their rights under the Act,

including the right to access, correct, or delete their data and to withdraw from the study at any time.

RESULTS

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
18-22 years old	57	23.8
23-27 years old	89	37.1
28-32 years old	49	20.4
33-37 years old	19	7.9
38-42 years old	11	4.6
43 years old and above	15	6.3
Gender		
Male	96	40.0
Female	133	55.4
LGBTQIA+	11	4.6
Educational Attainment		
Elementary	2	0.8
High School	60	25.0
College	93	38.8
College Graduate	82	34.2
Master's Degree	2	0.8
Doctorate Degree	1	0.4
Title		
Rank and File	122	67.8
Supervisory	55	30.6
Managerial	3	1.7
Monthly Income		
Below Php 8,000	32	13.3
Php 8,001 – Php 11,999	146	60.8
Php 12,000 – Php 15,999	32	13.3
Php 16,000 – Php 19,999	13	5.4
Php 20,000 and above	17	7.1
Total	240	100.0

Table 1 analyzes the respondents' profiles across various metrics. Regarding age distribution, most respondents fell within the 23–27 age group (37.1%), followed by the 18–22 age group (23.8%). The National Restaurant Association (2022) noted a higher proportion of young workers in the restaurant industry compared to the general economy, with 67% of workers under the age of thirty-five.

Regarding gender distribution, most respondents identified as Female (55.4%), followed by male (40%), and a smaller proportion as LGBTQIA+ (4.6%). The National Restaurant Association (2022) highlighted that more women are involved in managing restaurants

and food service businesses than in other sectors, attributing this trend to historical associations of caregiving roles with women.

Regarding educational attainment, most respondents had a college-level education (38.8%), followed by college graduates (34.2%). Managers (22%) and bartenders (21%) were noted as the two major restaurant career categories more likely to possess a bachelor's or graduate degree (National Restaurant Association, 2022).

Most respondents held rank-and-file positions (75.8%), with a smaller percentage in supervisory and managerial roles (12.1%). Entry-level roles were shared among individuals starting their careers, aiming to gain experience in their chosen professions (Herrity, 2024).

Regarding monthly income, most respondents fell within the P8,001 - P11,999 range (60.8%), followed by Below P8,000 and P12,000 - P15,999 (13.3%). De Castro (2017) noted that many graduates received gross monthly wages ranging from ₱5,000 to ₱15,000, which is considered a respectable wage for many individuals.

Table 2. Factors of Work Values in Terms of Self-Enhancement

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1) To assume a leadership position and have decision-making authority.	3.31	High
2) To be the head and tell others what to do.	3.01	Moderate
3) Get ahead in the working world and succeed more than others	3.30	High
4) To have ambition and be career oriented.	3.63	High
5) To organize others' work.	3.21	Moderate
6) To be successful at work.	3.72	High
Composite Mean	3.36	High

Legend: 1.00-1.74= Lowest Work Values; 1.75-2.49= Low Work Values; 2.50-3.24= Moderate Work Values; 3.25-4.00= High Work Values

Table 2 outlines the factors influencing work values related to self-enhancement. The highest mean value (M = 3.72, indicator 6) indicates a substantial work value associated with success in the workplace. Employees valuing success at work are often driven to advance in their careers, take on challenges, and actively seek growth opportunities. Siddiqui (2014) notes that job satisfaction is closely tied to feelings of achievement and motivation, with higher motivation correlating with increased goal-oriented behavior. Conversely, the lowest mean value (M = 3.01, indicator 2) reflects a moderate work value linked to directing others. Employees with this moderate value may excel in collaborative environments, preferring roles emphasizing teamwork and shared decision-making. De Spiegelaere et al. (2015) suggest that autonomy in work fosters creativity and innovation, essential for problem-solving and optimal work performance.

The composite mean ($M = 3.36$) signifies an overall high work value for self-enhancement. This result suggests that employees in the study are ambitious, goal-oriented, and focused on career progression, potentially benefiting from environments that support ambition and offer growth opportunities. Purc and Laguna (2019) propose that autonomy at work aligns with self-improvement values, facilitating goal attainment and control in the workplace. As highlighted by Li et al. (2022), employees driven by self-enhancement motives may exhibit increased work engagement under responsible leadership, driven by their desire to cultivate a positive self-image. By recognizing and nurturing these self-enhancement values, employers can foster job satisfaction, productivity, and a sense of competence among employees.

Table 3. Factors of Work Values in Terms of Self-Transcendence

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1) To be attentive to colleagues' needs and emotional state.	3.69	High
2) To dedicate attention to and listen to colleagues he/she does not esteem very much.	3.44	High
3) To respect colleagues' work and make an effort to understand their point of view even if he/she does not share it.	3.44	High
4) To be available when colleagues require his/her help.	3.75	High
5) To be open to forgiving a colleague who behaved incorrectly towards him/her.	3.47	High
6) To be loyal to colleagues.	3.58	High
Composite Mean	3.56	High

Legend: 1.00-1.74= Lowest Work Values; 1.75-2.49= Low Work Values; 2.50-3.24= Moderate Work Values; 3.25-4.00= High Work Values

Table 3 outlines the factors influencing work values related to self-transcendence. The highest mean value ($M = 3.75$, indicator 4) reflects a substantial work value associated with being available for colleagues in need. Employees valuing this aspect prioritize relationships and demonstrate a concern for others' well-being. Yaden et al. (2019) suggest that self-transcendence involves reducing self-focus and strengthening connections with others and the environment, fostering prosocial behavior and positive relationships. Conversely, the lowest mean value ($M = 3.44$, indicators 2 & 3) pertains to dedicating attention to and respecting colleagues, even those with whom one may not hold in high esteem. Employees valuing these aspects demonstrate sincerity, integrity, and active listening skills, enhancing communication and fostering interpersonal connections, as per Wong (2016).

The composite mean ($M = 3.56$) indicates a high work value for self-transcendence. Employees in this study exhibit a tolerant and appreciative attitude toward others, emphasizing teamwork, moral conduct, and a sense of belonging in the workplace. Creating an environment that supports such behaviors can reduce internal competition, enhance productivity, and boost job satisfaction. Individuals prioritizing self-transcendence may focus more on harmonious relationships and empathy than autonomy (Purc & Laguna, 2019). Self-transcendence values, such as empathy and altruism, have been linked to behaviors that meet others' needs and promote inclusivity and compassion (Reed & Haugan, 2021). Cultivating a workplace culture that encourages self-transcendence values can enhance cooperation, reduce conflicts, and foster a positive work environment.

Table 4. Factors of Work Values in Terms of Conservation

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1) To respect customs, rather than express his/her ideas.	3.18	Moderate
2) To do things in a traditional manner and use the customs learned.	3.29	High
3) To avoid expressing one's ideas if his/ her head or colleagues might criticize them.	2.59	Moderate
4) To adapt oneself to organizational requests, even if they go against his/her principals.	3.05	Moderate
5) Do not contradict his/her head or older colleagues.	2.98	Moderate
6) To work while remaining loyal to traditions and without adhering to continuous changes.	2.74	Moderate
Composite Mean	2.97	Moderate

Legend: 1.00-1.74= Lowest Work Values; 1.75-2.49= Low Work Values; 2.50-3.24= Moderate Work Values; 3.25-4.00= High Work Values

Table 4 outlines the factors impacting work values related to conservation. The highest mean value ($M = 3.29$, indicator 2) reflects a substantial work value associated with traditional practices and customs, indicating a commitment to conformity and upholding cultural traditions. Employees valuing this aspect prioritize adherence to organizational norms and cultural standards, often choosing to maintain the status quo rather than seeking increased autonomy (Purc & Laguna, 2019). Conversely, the lowest mean value ($M = 2.59$, indicator 3) pertains to avoiding expressing ideas for fear of criticism, indicating a moderate work value. Employees with this value may hold more conservative roles, potentially resulting in reduced engagement and productivity due to a fear of rejection and criticism within the company. The composite mean ($M = 2.97$) suggests a moderate work value for conservation, indicating that individuals from lower socioeconomic backgrounds

tend to exhibit more conservative behaviors. Adapting to changes and industry trends while preserving traditional values can enhance performance and productivity. Employees valuing conservation values may resist seeking job autonomy to maintain established social and organizational norms (Purc & Laguna, 2019).

Table 5. Factors of Work Values in Terms of Openness to Change

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1) To have stimulating work activities even if unexpected organizational changes are involved.	3.48	High
2) To be interested in his/her work, curious and attempt to more deeply understand every situation.	3.61	High
3) To know how to manage repetitive changes at work.	3.52	High
4) To learn different aspects of his/her work and acquire new competences.	3.67	High
5) To propose new ideas and express one's creativity within the workplace.	3.54	High
6) To seek out challenging objectives at work.	3.64	High
Composite Mean	3.52	High

Legend: 1.00-1.74= Lowest Work Values; 1.75-2.49= Low Work Values; 2.50-3.24= Moderate Work Values; 3.25-4.00= High Work Values

Table 5 outlines the factors impacting work values related to openness to change. The highest mean value (M = 3.67, indicator 4) reflects a substantial work value associated with learning new aspects of work and acquiring competencies, indicating a link between responsibility and openness to change. Employees valuing this aspect are proactive in adopting new skills, enhancing their career success and job satisfaction through self-directed learning (McArdle & Waters, 2017). Conversely, the lowest mean value (M = 3.48, indicator 1) pertains to finding stimulating work activities even amidst unexpected organizational changes, highlighting the importance of flexibility. Employees valuing this aspect demonstrate adaptability and willingness to embrace new challenges, traits employers value for their ability to handle diverse tasks effectively (Kossek & Thompson, 2016). The composite mean (M = 3.58) indicates a high work value for openness to change. This finding suggests that employees who embrace flexibility contribute positively to their workplace environment. Recognizing the importance of adaptability, employers value personnel who can build connections, maximize their roles effectively, and willingly pursue opportunities for growth and improvement in their careers. Individuals with high openness levels are better equipped to handle life changes, such as transitioning from office to remote work (Anderson et al., 2015).

Table 6. Factors of Work Values in Terms of Hedonism

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1) To select a job which consents one to enjoy him/herself and life.	3.72	High
2) To have a job which is fun and makes him/her feel good.	3.74	High
3) To find pleasant and entertaining occasions within the workplace.	3.71	High
Composite Mean	3.58	High

Legend: 1.00-1.74= Lowest Work Values; 1.75-2.49= Low Work Values; 2.50-3.24= Moderate Work Values; 3.25-4.00= High Work Values

Table 6 outlines the factors influencing work values related to hedonism. The highest mean value (M = 3.74, indicator 2) reflects a substantial work value associated with finding an enjoyable and fulfilling job, leading to increased motivation and job satisfaction. Employees who derive pleasure from their work environment tend to perform better, with contentment positively impacting their job performance (Peiró, 2019). Conversely, the lowest mean value (M = 3.71, indicator 3) pertains to seeking pleasant and entertaining occasions within the workplace, highlighting the importance of events like team lunches and team-building activities for fostering relationships and productivity. However, excessive focus on hedonistic activities can potentially decrease overall productivity. It may need to be balanced to avoid negative consequences (Plester & Hutchison, 2016). The composite mean (M = 3.72) suggests a high work value for hedonism, indicating that satisfaction and contentment can enhance job effectiveness. It is crucial to manage hedonistic activities to prevent procrastination and misuse of time within the workplace. Personality traits play a role in how individuals engage with hedonistic behaviors, with excessive pleasure-seeking potentially impacting wellbeing (Ksendzova et al., 2015). Balancing pleasure-seeking with productivity is essential for maintaining a positive work environment.

Table 7 outlines the factors influencing work values related to security. The highest mean value (M = 3.84, indicator 3) reflects a substantial work value associated with ensuring safety norms are upheld on the job site. This idea leads to heightened commitment and satisfaction among employees who feel valued and secure in a safe work environment. Safety performance impacts employee retention rates and organizational safety performance (Pinion et al., 2017; Brad-Harris et al., 2014). Contrariwise, the lowest mean value (M = 3.79, indicator 1) pertains to valuing guaranteed and stable employment, indicating that employees with secure positions are more committed, see themselves as successful within the company, and are motivated to work harder, benefiting from workplace advantages that support job progression and life fulfillment (Dessler, 2019).

Table 7. Factors of Work Values in Terms of Security

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1) To have a guaranteed and stable work position.	3.79	High
2) To work for an organization wherein employees' rights are protected.	3.83	High
3) To know that on-the-job site, safety norms and regulations concerning the prevention of accidents are respected.	3.84	High
Composite Mean	3.82	High

Legend: 1.00-1.74= Lowest Work Values; 1.75-2.49= Low Work Values; 2.50-3.24= Moderate Work Values; 3.25-4.00= High Work Values

The composite mean (M = 3.82) indicates an overall high work value for security, emphasizing the importance of job security in fostering employee commitment and dedication. Job security enhances engagement in work tasks and personal development, allowing employees to focus on their roles without fearing imminent job loss. Positive work-related attitudes like job satisfaction, engagement, and organizational dedication can substitute for job security (Baykal et al., 2023).

Table 8 shows the results of the difference in factors of work values according to age using the Kruskal-Wallis H test. The test found no statistically significant difference among age groups in terms of self-enhancement [H(5) = 2.579, p = .765]; self-transcendence [H(5) = 1.781, p = .879]; conservation [H(5) = 5.959, p = .310]; openness to change [H(5) = 7.221, p = .205]; hedonism [H(5) = 8.841, p = .116]; and lastly, in terms of security [H(5) = 8.000, p = .156] at the 5% significance level. This result implies that the changing nature of employees and societal advancements have concealed longstanding generational differences. Individuals of various ages in modern workplaces may have similar goals for professional progression, personal improvement, and job stability due to shared experiences in fast-changing sectors and economic situations. The tendency toward extended work tenure and postponed retirement has aided the age group's convergence of values. People who work longer have similar career phases and obstacles, such as mid-career changes, the need to refresh their skill set, and retirement planning concerns. A unified set of work ideals centered on stability and ongoing professional advancement are fostered by this shared trajectory (Fasbender et al., 2014).

Table 8. Differences in the Factors of Work Values According to Age.

Variables	Age	N	p-value	Remarks
Self-Enhancement	18-22	57	.765	Not Significant
	23-27	89		
	28-32	49		
	33-37	19		
	38-42	11		
	> 43	15		
Self-Transcendence	18-22	57	.879	Not Significant
	23-27	89		
	28-32	49		
	33-37	19		
	38-42	11		
	> 43	15		
Conservation	18-22	57	.310	Not Significant
	23-27	89		
	28-32	49		
	33-37	19		
	38-42	11		
	> 43	15		
Openness to Change	18-22	57	.205	Not Significant
	23-27	89		
	28-32	49		
	33-37	19		
	38-42	11		
	> 43	15		
Hedonism	18-22	57	.116	Not Significant
	23-27	89		
	28-32	49		
	33-37	19		
	38-42	11		
	> 43	15		
Security	18-22	57	.156	Not Significant
	23-27	89		
	28-32	49		
	33-37	19		
	38-42	11		
	> 43	15		

Note: *df*=5

Table 9 illustrates the gender-based differences in work values, particularly in conservation and security. The Kruskal-Wallis test indicates significant disparities in conservation [$H(2) = 13.464, p = .001$] and security [$H(2) = 8.295, p = .016$] across gender groups. LGBTQIA+ individuals exhibit distinct preferences in conservation and security

compared to males and females. LGBTQ individuals may prioritize inclusivity, unity, and environmental stewardship, potentially influenced by social norms and experiences of prejudice.

Table 9. Differences in the Factors of Work Values According to Gender

Variables	Sex	N	p-value	Remarks
Self-Enhancement	Male	96	.131	Not Significant
	Female	133		
	LGBTQIA+	11		
Self-Transcendence	Male	96	.170	Not Significant
	Female	133		
	LGBTQIA+	11		
Conservation	Male	96	.001	Significant
	Female	133		
	LGBTQIA+	11		
Openness to Change	Male	96	.314	Not Significant
	Female	133		
	LGBTQIA+	11		
Hedonism	Male	96	.429	Not Significant
	Female	133		
	LGBTQIA+	11		
Security	Male	96	.016	Significant
	Female	133		
	LGBTQIA+	11		

Note: df=2

In terms of self-enhancement, self-transcendence, openness to change, and hedonism, no significant differences were found among gender groups [$H(2) = 4.068, p = .131$; $H(2) = 3.546, p = .170$; $H(2) = 2.318, p = .314$; $H(2) = 1.693, p = .429$]. Gender identities do not significantly impact perceptions of work success, universalism, benevolence, skill development, or enjoyment of work. LGBTQ individuals may find solace and rejuvenation in natural environments, potentially due to experiences of discrimination, as nature can offer respite and reflection (Matsick, 2024). Organizations can enhance workplace inclusivity for LGBTQ employees by implementing LGBT-friendly policies and fostering an environment that respects individual rights and social justice (Everly & Schwarz, 2015; Mor Barak et al., 2016).

Table 10 presents the differences in work values based on educational attainment using the Kruskal-Wallis H test. A significant difference was observed in self-enhancement [$H(5) = 11.428, p = .044$], with varying mean rank values across educational levels. Notably, individuals with higher degrees, such as doctorates, exhibited self-enhancement ideals emphasizing long-term goals and success. Higher education may foster competitiveness

and goal-setting behaviors, impacting how individuals evaluate success and pursue professional achievements.

Table 10. Differences in the Factors of Work Values According to Educational Attainment

Variables	Education	N	p-values	Remarks
Self-Enhancement	Elementary	2	.044	Significant
	High School	60		
	College	93		
	College Graduate	82		
	Master's Degree	2		
	Doctorate Degree	1		
Self-Transcendence	Elementary	2	.214	Not Significant
	High School	60		
	College	93		
	College Graduate	82		
	Master's Degree	2		
	Doctorate Degree	1		
Conservation	Elementary	2	.234	Not Significant
	High School	60		
	College	93		
	College Graduate	82		
	Master's Degree	2		
	Doctorate Degree	1		
Openness to Change	Elementary	2	.065	Not Significant
	High School	60		
	College	93		
	College Graduate	82		
	Master's Degree	2		
	Doctorate Degree	1		
Hedonism	Elementary	2	.538	Not Significant
	High School	60		
	College	93		
	College Graduate	82		
	Master's Degree	2		
	Doctorate Degree	1		
Security	Elementary	2	.390	Not Significant
	High School	60		
	College	93		
	College Graduate	82		
	Master's Degree	2		
	Doctorate Degree	1		

Note: *df*=5

Conversely, no significant differences were found among educational attainment groups in terms of self-transcendence [$H(5) = 7.095$, $p = .214$], conservation [$H(5) = 6.824$, $p = .234$], openness to change [$H(5) = 10.392$, $p = .065$], hedonism [$H(5) = 4.083$, $p = .538$], and security [$H(5) = 5.214$, $p = .390$]. This finding suggests that educational attainment

levels do not significantly influence values related to building relationships, traditional and adaptable traits, hedonistic activities, and workplace security.

Table 11. Differences in the Factors of Work Values According to Job Title

Variables	Job Title	N	p-values	Remarks
Self-Enhancement	Rank and File	122	.001	Significant
	Supervisory	55		
	Managerial	3		
Self-Transcendence	Rank and File	122	.462	Not Significant
	Supervisory	55		
	Managerial	3		
Conservation	Rank and File	122	.792	Not Significant
	Supervisory	55		
	Managerial	3		
Openness to Change	Rank and File	122	.011	Significant
	Supervisory	55		
	Managerial	3		
Hedonism	Rank and File	122	.332	Not Significant
	Supervisory	55		
	Managerial	3		
Security	Rank and File	122	.907	Not Significant
	Supervisory	55		
	Managerial	3		

Note: $df=4$; $*p < .05$

Table 11 presents the disparities in work values based on job titles using the Kruskal-Wallis H test. A significant distinction was detected in self-enhancement [$H(2) = 13.144$, $p = .001$], with diverse mean rank values across job roles. Individuals in managerial positions exhibited stronger self-enhancement ideals than those in rank-and-file roles, indicating the impact of job titles on self-perception and external recognition (Grant et al., 2015). Titles like "CEO" or "Manager" often signify authority and leadership, influencing one's sense of importance and influence within the organization and community. Likewise, a notable difference was noted in openness to change [$H(2) = 9.065$, $p = .011$] among job titles, with managerial roles displaying higher openness to change than rank-and-file positions. Job titles can mirror a proactive stance towards change and innovation, necessitating adaptability and receptiveness to novel ideas and technologies (Arieli & Tenne-Gazit, 2017). This openness to change is linked to creativity and innovation, as individuals in such roles are expected to seek and implement innovative solutions actively. Contrariwise, no significant distinctions among job title groups concerning self-transcendence, conservation, hedonism, and security values were found. While job titles signal authority and leadership levels, they do not notably impact values tied to universalism, benevolence, traditional or adaptable attitudes, hedonistic behaviors, or

workplace security. Job titles serve as identifiers of one is standing within the organizational hierarchy, potentially shaping self-identity and intra-organizational relationships. A self-reflective job title can aid individuals in establishing their distinct identities and fostering group acceptance and relationship fortification within the workplace (Grant et al., 2015).

Table 12. Differences in the Factors of Work Values According to Monthly Income

Variables	Income	N	p-values	Remarks
Self-Enhancement	Below P8,000	32	.031	Significant
	P8,001-P11,999	146		
	P12,000-P15,999	32		
	P16,000-P19,999	13		
	P20,000 and above	17		
Self-Transcendence	Below P8,000	32	.902	Not Significant
	P8,001-P11,999	146		
	P12,000-P15,999	32		
	P16,000-P19,999	13		
	P20,000 and above	17		
Conservation	Below P8,000	32	.152	Not Significant
	P8,001-P11,999	146		
	P12,000-P15,999	32		
	P16,000-P19,999	13		
	P20,000 and above	17		
Openness to Change	Below P8,000	32	.052	Not Significant
	P8,001-P11,999	146		
	P12,000-P15,999	32		
	P16,000-P19,999	13		
	P20,000 and above	17		
Hedonism	Below P8,000	32	.153	Not Significant
	P8,001-P11,999	146		
	P12,000-P15,999	32		
	P16,000-P19,999	13		
	P20,000 and above	17		
Security	Below P8,000	32	.399	Not Significant
	P8,001-P11,999	146		
	P12,000-P15,999	32		
	P16,000-P19,999	13		
	P20,000 and above	17		

Table 12 displays the variations in work values based on monthly income using the Kruskal-Wallis H test. A significant difference was found in self-enhancement [$H(4) = 10.642$, $p = .031$], with individuals earning P16,000 - P19,999 showing distinct self-enhancement ideals compared to other income brackets. Higher incomes are often linked to more significant opportunities for career advancement and personal development, aligning with the pursuit of challenging professional goals and increased recognition.

Income can serve as a metric of competence and progress for those valuing self-improvement, bolstering their sense of accomplishment and self-worth (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2021).

Conversely, no significant differences among income groups concerning self-transcendence, conservation, openness to change, hedonism, and security values were observed. Monthly income does not significantly correlate with values related to universalism, benevolence, traditional or adaptable attitudes, receptiveness to change, indulgent activities, or workplace security. While higher income can reflect perceived job competence and satisfaction, mental health issues like anxiety and depression can impact individuals' economic choices and job performance (Ridley et al., 2020). Moreover, individuals with better wages and job prospects tend to engage more in job-related training, enhancing their earning potential and adaptability to evolving job markets and technological advancements (OECD, 2019). Improving mental and physical health can also influence income levels as individuals strive for personal growth and wellbeing.

CONCLUSIONS

The examination of the results of the demographic profile reveals that most of the respondents are aged 23-27 Years Old (37.1%), Female (55.4%), attained College Level (38.8%), Rank and File Job Title (75.8%), and have P8,001-P11,999 (60.8%) Monthly Income. Researchers, therefore, conclude that employees in Olongapo City possess High Work Values that significantly affect their working performance, colleague relationships, and a job in which they are passionate and willing to learn as well as enjoy and feel secure. Also, Researchers found out that traditional and adapted values brought by diverse cultures moderately influence their principles and attitudes, which implies a good characteristic that employees in Olongapo City can adjust to the changing needs of the working environment rather than being averse to change and remain traditional.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The researchers recommend creating a work atmosphere where job satisfaction, work-life balance, and employee wellbeing are top priorities. Employees are more likely to demonstrate excellent work ethics and a strong dedication to their roles when they feel appreciated and supported.

The researchers suggest that company owners use this research to help their staff members' attitudes and work ethics grow. Researchers might recommend implementing programs that support and strengthen the work values of restaurant staff members and can improve output, lower turnover, and increase job satisfaction.

Lastly, researchers recommend this study to future researchers who would like to pursue this kind of concept to extend their knowledge and assess the work values of restaurant employees, which might help them adopt and apply professional character and well-

being. This study serves as a basis and reference for future researchers interested in exploring work values in the hospitality industry sectors.

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